

***EXAMINING THE INFLUENCE OF COACH-PLAYER RELATIONSHIP ON
VOLLEYBALL PLAYER PERFORMANCE: A CASE STUDY OF THE HADIYA ZONE
VOLLEYBALL PROJECT***

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the impact of coach-player relationships on volleyball performance in the Hadiya Zone Volleyball Project. It employs a mixed-method design combining quantitative and qualitative approaches to gain a comprehensive understanding. Data is gathered from primary sources like questionnaires, interviews, and field observations, as well as secondary sources such as yearly reports and office manuals. The study focuses on two training centers: Gombora Woreda and Anlemon Woreda, with a target population of 43 (including 2 coaches, 1 manager, and 40 players). The sample size is 23. Quantitative data is analyzed using SPSS, Version 20, with results presented through descriptive statistics like frequency and percentage.

The study reveals both positive and negative effects of coach-player relationships on volleyball performance. Players reported mutual respect and open communication among themselves, but faced challenges in communicating with the management. Additionally, players lacked recreational interactions outside of practice. They expressed dissatisfaction with the supply of volleyball facilities and support from the center in areas like sportswear, transportation, medical assistance, and financial backing.

Key -Words: *Interpersonal communication, Motivation, performance, Positive reinforcement, self-confidence*

1. BACK GROUND OF THE STUDY

The sport of volleyball has continued to increase in participation since its inception over one hundred years ago. Volleyball has become one of the most widely played participant sports in the world with over 200 million players. The number of participants rivals the number of soccer participants (250 million) reported by the Federation International de Football Association (Mageau & Vallerand, 2003). Another indication of the worldwide appeal of all forms of volleyball was the inclusion of beach volleyball as an Olympic sport in 1996. Potential reasons for the popularity of volleyball are that the sport requires a minimal amount of equipment and individuals can participate throughout their lives at a variety of skill levels.

Baron & Kerr 2002 argued that there are a number of important relationships in sport involving players, coaches, parents and partners but that knowledge of these relationships, both in theoretical and empirical terms, is limited. The last decade has witnessed a significant increase in research focusing on relationships in sport. Such work has facilitated the development of understanding of the nature and importance of these relationships. A coach who fails to acknowledge the importance of the coach- player relationships risks not develops their players to their full potential. A series of qualitative studies have been conducted to investigate this relationship [e.g. Jowett & Don Carolis 2003, and Jowett & Cockerill, 2002]. In a sport context there are many personal relationships [e.g. Coach-parent, player-player, and player- partner] that can impact on performance, but the coach - player relationship is considered to be particularly crucial.

The coach- player relationship is not an add-on to, or by - product of, the coaching process, nor is it based on the player performance, age or gender instead it is the foundation of coaching, the coach and the player intentionally develop a relationship, which is characterized by a growing appreciation and respect for each other as individuals. This research will be conducted at SNNPRG, Hadiya Zone Volleyball Project, and Ethiopia.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Volleyball has become one of the most widely played participant sports in the world with over 200 million players. The player-coach relationship has been somewhat limited given the

potential that exists for coaches to influence both the values and behaviors of players. Michael, 2009 stated that the relationship has three major components: a technical component, a social-psychological component, and a spiritual component, and conclude that players change because of the influence of their coaches.

According to Burke 2001, the potential influence is based on coaches viewing their players as possessions and on players displaying loyalty and obedience without questioning the restrictions established by the coach. "The truth is, if you're a coach, you have authority over the players". They further explain that authority is the legitimate use of power over others. It is apparent that there is room for subjective evaluation in such a statement as to just what "legitimate" use would be.

The approach a coach uses with one player may not be interpreted in the same way by another. Baron & Kerr 2002 found that players interpret coaches' actions differently; therefore, effective coaching behavior should vary as the characteristics of the athletes and the situation changes. Although coaches are in direct contact with athletes on a day-to-day basis and are in an optimal position to teach and model appropriate values and ethics in sport, coaches receive minimal education in this area.

The previous study was focused on interpersonal relationship of players and coaches on the performance regard to competition of football athletes. But this study would mainly focused on the effects of coaches and players relationship on volleyball players performance as well as the management has an advantage on team performance and team success in the Hadiya Zone selected centers of Gomboro woreda and Analemo woreda

1.4 Research Questions

1. What are the Examining the Influence of Coach-Player Relationship on Volleyball Player Performance: A Case Study of the Hadiya Zone Volleyball Project?
2. What are the effects of players and coach's relationship on volleyball performance of the training center in Hadiya Zone Volleyball Project.
3. How to investigate the effects of players and general management relationship on volleyball performance of management and the coach in Hadiya Zone Volleyball Project.

1.3 Objective of the Study

1.3.1 General Objective

This study examining the Influence of Coach-Player Relationship on Volleyball Player Performance: A Case Study of the Hadiya Zone Volleyball Project

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of this study were to: -

1. Examine the effects of players and player's relationship on volleyball performance in Hadiya Zone Volleyball Project.
2. Examine the effects of players and coach's relationship on volleyball performance of the training center in Hadiya Zone Volleyball Project.
3. Investigate the effects of players and general management relationship on volleyball performance of management and the coach in Hadiya Zone Volleyball Project.

1.5 Significance of the Study

The study would support and enrich the interpersonal relationship of players in Hadiya Zone Volleyball Project. To this end the significance of the study served a coaching guide line for the study area, contributed and maintained professional attitude and relationship among players & the sport association community, provided a valuable resource to coaches, players, sport psychology consultants, researchers.

1.6 Delimitation of the Study

The study limited to Hadiya Zone selected centers of volleyball project. In addition to this, the study is delimited only to investigate the problems related to inter- relationship of players in the training center of Gomboro woreda and Anlemoworeda.

1.7. Limitations of the study

In this study difficulties described as follows: most of documents, those concerned with volleyball sport was written in Amharic. To translate in to the required instruction language (English) takes longer period of time. Another problem was some respondent's reluctance to

cooperate due to disclosing information may lead to negative effect on their job performances.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter includes Description of the Study area, research design, source of data, and instrument of data collection, target population, methods of sampling, sample size and method of data analysis.

3.2 Description of the Study area

Figure 3.1 Hadiya Zone Map

Source: (Hadiya Zone Administration Documentation)

The study Zone, Hadiya is one of the Zones in the SNNPR of the Ethiopia. It is situated in the western margin of the Great Ethiopian Rift Valley and at the fringe of the Gurage mountains in the northern part of the region. Its absolute location is roughly between 7045'N and 38028'E. Its capital, Hossana, is 232 km away from Addis Ababa, the capital of the Ethiopia and it is also 168kms and 200kms away from the capital of the SNNPR, Hawassa through Alaba- Danboya-Anegacha and Durame- Shenshicho, respectively. Hadiya zone is bordered in the south by Kembata–Tembaro Zone and Alaba Zone, on the west by the Omo

River which separates it from Oromia Region and the Yem Special Woreda, in the north by Gurage and Silite Zones, and in the east by the Oromia Region. According to the data collected from National Metrological Service Agency Hossana branch *nearly two-thirds (64.7%)* of the Zone lies in the WoinaDega agro-climatic zone whereas 23.7% and 11.6% of the total land area of the zone lies in the Dega and Kolla agro-climatic nature respectively. Hadiya zone receives seasonal rainfall amount ranging between 469.98 and 156.66 mm annually in summer, season from June to August locally named as “Hagayye”.

3.3. Research Design

In this study the researcher used the specific procedures involved in the research process: data collection, data analysis, and report writing. Besides to this the researcher also used descriptive method of research and both qualitative and quantitative approaches of the data. The mixed method designs were useful to capture the best of both quantitative and qualitative approaches and to provide a better understanding of research problems than either approach alone. In this design, the investigator collects both forms of data at the same time and then integrates the information in the interpretation of the overall results.

3.4 Source of Data

This study used both primary and secondary sources of data. The use of these instruments proved to be helpful since it facilitated triangulation of information from the different sources.

3.4.1. Primary source

The primary data was questionnaire, face-to-face interviews and field observation.

3.4.2. Secondary source

The secondary data was yearly reports and office manuals of the training centers.

3.5 Instrument for data collection

The primary data was collected through questionnaire that completed by the respondents of the selected sectors, filled by the players and coach of the center, totally twenty-three questionnaires was distributed and besides face-to-face interviews with the relevant officers who leads the sectors in the selected sectors and conducted with the general manager of the center and field observation. The secondary data was collected from yearly reports and office manuals of the training centers.

3.6 Target Population of the Study

In this study there are two training centers namely Gomboro and Analemo woreda. The target population of the selected training centers was 43. These include 2 coaches, 1 manager and 40 players.

3.7 Sampling techniques

In this study the researcher selected purposive sampling technique; because it enables the researcher to generate meaningful insights that help to gain a deeper understanding of the research phenomena by selecting the most informative participants that is satisfactory to its specific needs. Therefore, the researcher was focused on these two centers which have enough team, very popular in nature and have greater effects to influence the Zone's overall social, political and economic issues.

3.8 Sample Size of the Study

The sample size of the study refers to a subset of the population that the researcher aims to generalize the results to. In this particular study, the researcher deliberately selected 10 players from each center, as well as 1 coach from each center, and additionally included 1 manager from the Hadiya zone volleyball center. Consequently, the sample size for this study consisted of 22 individuals, which represents 43% of the target population.

3.9 Methods of Data Analysis

To simplify the data analysis, after the collection of both primary and secondary data information from the training center, the quantitative data would have been entered in to the statistical package for social science (SPSS), Version 20. The answer received from investigation of the center was tabulated and interpreted by taking descriptive statistics results by Frequency and percentage. The result from the interview was also properly arranged and discussed in the study. Finally, the data gathered by field observation were discussed in the study.

4. ANALYSIS, DISCUSSION, AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Presentation and Analysis of the data gathered through Questionnaire

The data was obtained from twenty players, two coaches and one general manager of the training center gave sufficient ground to conclude about the effects of coaches and players relationship on volleyball players performance. For the sake of easy interpretation and clarity of understanding the data have been presented in the following subsections. Analysis of back ground information of

players, analysis of questionnaire responses of players, analysis of questionnaire responses the coach of the training center, analysis of interview responses of the general manager of training center and Interpretation and discussion of field observation.

Figure 4.1: Distribution of sampled players' respondents by their sex

Source: (Result of SPSS)

The above fig. 4.1 explains that respondent's information, as indicated in the first part of this figure, a total of 22 players were involved in the study. Moreover, their information was analyzed as below regarding the sex of respondents' 22 (100%) players were male. From this the researcher understood that males were dominant participants in the training center.

Figure 4.2: Distribution of sampled players' respondents by their age group

Source: Source: (Result of SPSS)

Fig. 4.2 shows the vast number 16-17 (45.45%) of players. Similarly, 8 (36.36%) and 4 (18.18%) of players are swings from 18-19 and 20-21 years of age respectively. This implies that all respondents can survive challenges that happened in the training center.

Figure 4.3: Distribution of sampled players' respondents by their training age

Source: Source: (Result of SPSS)

According to the above figure 4.3, 6 (27.27%) of players training age in Hadiya zone were less than one year, in the same way, 10 (45.45%) 4 (18.18%) and 2 (9.1%) of players training age 2, <3 year and 3 years of age. Here the respondents can share idea easily; because of they have enough experience.

Table 4.1: Members of the team would rather go out on their own than get together as a team

Rating	Frequency	Percent
Agree	6	27.3
Neutral	3	13.6
Disagree	11	50.0
Strongly disagree	2	9.1
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

As it is indicated in table 4.1, 11 (50%) of respondent players responded that they disagreed. Among the participants 6 (27%) have agreed to the item while 3 (14%) remained undecided whereas the remaining 2(9%) participant players have strongly disagreed. Therefore, we can conclude that most of the participant players mentioned the members of the team should have to unite as a team.

Table 4.2: - The team is united in trying to reach its goal for the performance

Rating	Frequency	Percent
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Strongly Agree	10	45.5
Agree	6	27.3
Neutral	2	9.1
Disagree	4	18.2
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

According to the information in table 4.2, 10 (46%) participant players have strongly agreed while 6 (27%) players agreed to the item. Only 4 (18%) participant players disagreed and the remaining 2 (9%) players had not decided to the statement. In general, the researcher concluded that most of the respondents had united in trying to reach its goals for performance.

Table 4.3: In the team there is a mutual respect between players and players

Rating	Frequency	Percent
Strongly agree	8	36.4
Agree	10	45.5
Disagree	4	18.2
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

As can be seen from the above table 4.3, 10 (46%) of the players agreed with the item. However, 12 (34%) of participant players were also strongly agreed to the statement only 8 (23%) of respondents had not decided. In general, it could be concluded that there was a mutual respect among players.

Table 4.4: The team members did communicate freely about each player responsibilities during competition or training practice

Rating	Frequency	Percent
Agree	6	27.3
Neutral	2	9.1
Disagree	12	54.5
Strongly disagree	2	9.1
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

As it can be shown in table 4.4, 12 (55%) of participant players disagreed to the item. Among these, 6 (27%) of players have agreed to the item, 2 (9%) respondent players had not decided. The remaining 2 (9%) respondent players replied strongly disagreed. The above finding indicates that majority of the respondent players point out they couldn't freely communicate on each players responsibility during competition or training practices.

Table 4.5: In case if one of the team members has problems in practice, everyone wants to help, so we could get back together again

Rating	Frequency	Percent
Strongly agree	10	45.5
Agree	4	18.2
Neutral	2	9.1
Disagree	3	13.6
Strongly Disagree	3	13.6
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

Based on the data on table 4.5, 10 (46%) players have strongly agreed. While, 4 (18%) players replied agreed to the case if one of the team members has problems in practice, everyone wants to help, so we could get back together again. Whereas 3 (14%) of respondents have strongly disagreed and 3 (14%) players replied their disagreement. The remaining 2 (9%) have not decided. Therefore, this statement implies that every member of the team has the spirit to help each other when the team in counters a problem.

Table 4.6: Members of the team stick together outside practices and competition

Rating	Frequency	Percent
Strongly agree	5	22.7
Neutral	10	45.5
Disagree	2	9.1
Strongly disagree	5	22.7
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

According to the above table 4.6, 10 (46%) of participant players have not decided to the item. Among respondents 5 (23%) player also strongly agreed while 5 (23%) players have strongly disagreed to the statement. The remaining 5 (23%) of participant replied they disagreed. This shows that most of the players had not the habit of recreating themselves with each other out of the time of practice and computation.

Table 4.7: All the team members take responsibilities for any loss or poor performance by the player

Rating	Frequency	Percent
Strongly agree	9	40.9
Agree	10	45.5
Strongly disagree	3	13.6
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

Table 4.7, shows that 10 (46%) players have strongly agreed, 9 (41%) players replied they agreed to the statement, among the participants 3 (14%) respondents had strongly disagreed to the item. All in all, this implies that most of the respondents pointed out all the players took the responsibility for the loss or poor performance of the team.

Table 4.8 Participation of players in decision making

Rating	Frequency	Percent
Always	2	9.1
Often	3	13.6
Occasionally	3	13.6
Seldom	2	9.1
Never	12	54.5
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

The above table 4.8, indicates that the same number of players 3(14%) responded that their coach allows them to participate in decision making often and occasionally. Again the same number of respondents 2(9%) said that they are allowed always and seldom. On the other hand, 12(55%) responded they are never allowed. From this the researcher concluded that most of the players never allowed participating in decision making in Hadiya zone volley ball project.

Table 4.9: Favoring of the coach to some players

Items	Frequency	Percent
Often	3	13.6
Occasionally	15	68.2
Seldom	4	18.2
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

As in table 4.9, most of the respondents 15 (68.18%) responded that their coach favors some players from the other occasionally. Whereas the 4 (18.18%) responded the coach does his sometimes and the same number of respondents 3 (13.64%) replied the coach shows this seldom. This indicated that the coach favors some players than the other, this made biasedness among players.

Researchers have investigated the factors that may influence and athlete's perceptions and evaluation of coaching behaviors (Amorose & Horn, 2000; Beam et al., 2004; Chelladurai, 1984; Hollembeak & Amorose, 2005; Sherman, Fuller, & Speed, 2000). Subsequently, it has been found that athletes who felt more compatible with their coach experienced fewer negative cognitive/attentional and somatic effects from their coach's behaviors. Athletes who felt more compatible also felt more supported by their coach and evaluated his/her communication ability more favorably.

Table 4.10: The fair treatment of players by the coach

Items	Frequency	Percent
Always	15	68.2
Occasionally	3	13.6
Seldom	2	9.1
Never	2	9.1
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

The above table 4.10 shows majority of the participant players 15 (68.18%) of the participant players believe that the coach treats them equally and fairly. 3 (13.64%) of the players said occasionally. But the remaining 2 (9.09%) player said their coach seldom treats them equally and fairly. Finally 2

(9.09%) of the players believe that they are never treated equally and fairly. This implies that players fairly treated by the coach.

The nature of the coach is important to consider when examining the intricacies of the coach-athlete relationship and how coaching leader behaviors are significantly related to team outcomes. Some reasons for this are that providing contingent positive feedback and reinforcement along with socially supportive behaviors have been associated with satisfied athletes. Further, the way a coach behaves affects how an players will perceive and recall these behaviors at some point and then eventually how they will come to recognize their coaches behaviors. Finally, there are the fundamental needs for competence, autonomy, and relatedness, and if these needs are not properly met, that can impact an individual's intrinsic motivation (Amorose& Horn, 2000, 2001; Hollembeak&Amorose, 2005).

Table 4.11: Motivating players when they perform well

Items	Frequency	Percent
Always	2	9.1
Often	7	31.8
Occasionally	9	40.9
Seldom	4	18.2
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

Table 4.11, shows that 9 (41%) of the players stated that the coach sometimes puts the suggestions made by the players in to operation. 7 (32%) of players responded that the coach often, makes in to operation and 2 (9%) players replied always. 4(18%) players replied seldom their coach applies their suggestion. This implies that they were not given attention by the concerning body, in order to motivate players when they perform well.

If the athletes' goals, personality, and beliefs are consistent with those of their coach, the interaction of the individuals will likely be satisfactory to both parties, therein producing a positive interpersonal atmosphere. Conversely, a downbeat interaction between the coach and the athlete can also create a negative interpersonal atmosphere, which fosters the likelihood of their being an unproductive and unbeneficial, negative self-fulfilling prophesy.

Table 4.12 Participating players in sketching strategies

Items	Frequency	Percent
Often	10	45.5
Occasionally	7	31.8
Seldom	3	13.6
Never	2	9.1
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

As can be seen in the above table 4.12, 10 (45.45%) responded often to the statement, 7 (31.81%) of players said that the coach sometimes asks their opinion. The remaining 3 (13.64%) replied seldom to the item. Whereas 2 (9.1) of the players responded that they are not allowed to give their opinion about the strategies at all. This concluded that the players had participating in sketching strategies so that they could get clue/ hint each other.

There is a necessary harmonic component within the coach-athlete relationship. Poczwadowski, Barott, &Henschen, (2002) reported that “The coach-athlete relationship as a recurring pattern of three parts: (1) mutual care between the athletes, (2) the presence of relationship-oriented interactions and activates, and (3) specific meaning which the athletes and coaches attach to their relationship.” Their findings also found the more positive, compatible, and strong the coach-athlete relationship, the more beneficial experience the athletes will have in their respective sport (Mgaewa 203).

Table 4.13: Coach shows me clap hands when I perform well

Items	Frequency	Percent
Always	5	22.7
Often	2	9.1
Occasionally	10	45.5
Seldom	5	22.7
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

As indicated in table 4.13, 10(45.45%) of players replied occasionally to the item, 5(22.73%)

of players also replied always to the question and 2 (9.1%) of players replied 'often' the remaining 5(22.72%) of players responded seldom. This implied that there was no appreciation accordingly by Coach to clap hands when performance was well.

Table 4.14: The coaches help in solving personal problems of players

Items	Frequency	Percent
Often	3	13.6
Occasionally	12	54.5
Seldom	7	31.8
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

The above table 4.14, shows that 12 (54.55%) players revealed that their coach helps them to solve their problems occasionally. 7 (31.81%) of participant players rated seldom, only 3 (13.64%) of players responded their coach does this often.

Table 4.15: The help of the coach to make players train themselves

Items	Frequency	Percent
Occasionally	10	45.5
Seldom	8	36.4
Never	4	18.2
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

According to table 4.15, 10 (45.5%) of players responded that their coach allows them to practice their own ways of training. Whereas 8(36.4%) of players responded seldom. The rest 4 (18.1%) players responded they never allowed to do so. Here the coach guided them sometimes to make players train themselves. Hence, it makes them to develop confidence alone.

Considering how important the agreement of these aspects has been shown to be in leading to optimal performance and group satisfaction with athletic coaches in practice and in competition. More than enough to warrant examining the uniqueness of the strength coach-athlete relationship and how group satisfaction and effective training when performing

strength and conditioning could carry over to more effective athletic practices and competitions. Players develop the impacts of coaches and players relationship on volleyball sport performance over the course of their careers, but none is closer than that formed with the coach and/or team-mates. Furthermore, (poczwardowski, Barott, and pergoy (2002) found that the effects of coaches and players relationship on volleyball players performance formed with the coach had a great influence on player's training processes, performance outcomes, and aspects of their private lives.

Table 4.16: The professional relationship of the coach with player

Items	Frequency	Percent
Always	16	72.7
Often	3	13.6
Occasionally	3	13.6
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

According to table 4.16, 16 (72.72%) of respondent players replied their coach has good relationship with them always. 3 (13.64%) of players also replied often to the question. The remaining 3 (13.64%) of players responded occasionally. Therefore, it can be concluded that the coach of the team had good professional relationships with all players.

Table 4.17: Improving team spirit by the coach

Items	Frequency	Percent
Always	16	72.7
Often	3	13.6
Occasionally	3	13.6
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

Based on the above table 4.17, 16 (72.72%) responded that their coach always tries to improve cooperation among the team mates. 3 (13.64%) replied the coach does this often. Whereas 3 (13.64%) of also replied occasionally. This statement reveals that the coach

encouraged the players to help each other to develop the effects of coaches and players relationship on volleyball sport performance among them by improving team spirit.

Table 4.18: Supply of volleyball equipment to the players by the management

Rating	Frequency	Percent
Satisfied	4	18.2
Not satisfied	10	45.5
Neutral	8	36.4
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

As indicated in the above table 4.18, 10 (45.5%) respondents were not satisfied with the supply of training equipment and 8 (36.4%) participant players were also neutral, whereas, 4 (18.1%) respondent did not decide to the statement. From this the researcher could infer that most of players were not satisfied by the player equipment supplied by the management.

Table 4.19: Meetings arranged by the management to make players meet their parents

Rating	Frequency	Percent
Satisfied	6	27.3
Not satisfied	12	54.5
Neutral	4	18.2
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

Based on the data in table 4.19, 12 (54.54%) of participant players are not satisfied by the management of the center schedule of meeting their parents. On the other hand, 6 (27.3%) players are satisfied. Whereas the remaining 4 (18.2%) of the players did not decide with the statement. From the above responses, most of the players said the management of the training center did not organize enough time to meet their parents.

Table 4.20: Supply of Volleyball facilities

Rating	Frequency	Percent
Satisfied	2	9.1
Not satisfied	12	54.5
Neutral	8	36.4
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

The data on the above table 4.20, shows that, 12 (54.54%) of players were not satisfied, likewise, 8(36.4%) participant players had not decided to the item. The remaining 2 (9.09%) respondents were satisfied. From this the researcher concluded that they could not be satisfied by the supply of volleyball facilities such as sport wear, transport, medical, financial support to the team by the center.

Figure 4.4: Insurance of players in the center

Source: (Result of SPSS)

The above Fig. 4.4, 22 (100%) said no to the insurance of the players. This shows that all the responded players in Hadiya zone training center are not insured for any damage they encountered.

Table 4.21: the effects of players and management relationship

Rating	Frequency	Percent
Satisfied	3	13.6
Not satisfied	11	50.0
Neutral	8	36.4
Total	22	100.0

Source: (Result of SPSS)

As it can be seen in the above table 4.21, the players responded that are not satisfied 11(50%) and 8 (36.36%) and are neutral, On the contrary 3 (13.64%) players were satisfied with the management approach. This implies that telling the level of their satisfaction with regard to the impacts of players and management relationship on volleyball sport performance had not satisfied.

Figure 4.5 Follow up of the management in training

Source: (Result of SPSS)

According to the above fig. 4.5, 14 (63.64%) players responded that the management of the training center had visited them during training sessions. On the other hand, 8 (36.36%) of players replied that the management of the training center did not follow up them during trainings. This indicates that majority of the respondents had been visited by management during training session.

Figure 4.6: Salary given to the players

Source: (Result of SPSS)

As it is indicated in fig. 4.6, 22 (100%) respondents said no. This implies that the training centers of the study area did not provide any salary to players. So that no one has hope to stay at this center; as well as they will search another access for the future.

Figure 4.7: The incentive gives by the management of the training center

Source: (Result of SPSS)

As shown in the above fig. 4.7, all the players 22 (100%) responded that they did not get any motivation. This shows that there was no any incentive given by the management of the training center to the trainee. Another dimension, training is utilized to bolster the players. Here the strength of a personal trainer may guide its some mobility flexibility exercises that were just introduced and clarifies training priorities to be worked on (Mgaewa 203).

4.2 Interview responses Discussion

The interview was made with a team manager of Hadiya Zone Volleyball Project training center. The following texts are the extracts of the response given by the team manager.

In the first question, the general manager was asked to tell his working experience. Then he said that he has more than six years of experience working as teacher and staff member.

For question which asked to suggest his role as a general manager to the training center, from this item, he said that he has different duties and responsibility in facilitating the overall activities of the athletes. For instance, he mentioned the following points: to arrange all travel and accommodations for players and the coach, to provide appropriate information to players, coaches and parents, to ensure provision for players, to arrive at appropriate time at venues.

He responded that, the center provides different facilities and volleyball equipment's to the coach and the players. For instance, facilities like transport, medical and equipment's like sport wears and fitness materials had provided. For the final question that was asked the general manager to suggest solutions to improve the effects of the players with coaches and managers. According to this item he suggested that the effects of coaches and players relationship on volleyball sport performance are very important for one team to perform successfully. In order to achieve this, it is better to enhance the players' relationships by making open communication among each other, establishing good productive relationships requires a considerable amount of effort, and cooperation, provide good facilities and equipment.

4.3. Discussion of field observation

The field observation was made at Hadiya Zone Volleyball Project field area during training sessions. The researcher observed the effects of coaches and players relationship on volleyball sport performance during practical training in most cases, the practical training sessions are conducted for an hour and two days a week. At this time the researcher observed the following points: the players' relationship and interpersonal skills, the coaching ability and communications at practice session, the personal characteristics. coaching style/ coaching behavior, regarding to the player relationship and interpersonal skills during practical session. Based on that the researcher has observed the following points: there is mutual respect among the player and players and coach, the coach treats all player equally and fairly.

The other observation was on the coach's ability and communications during practical session. From the above observations, the researcher understands that the players have good communication during training session. The coaching style and coaching behavior of the player. The researcher found that players preferred coaching style was a key issue facing

coach- player's interactions prior to performance. Coaching style has important implications in terms of communication and mental preparation. Both coaches and players perceived that establishing a positive environment was an essential aspect of a coach-player relationship. Performance suffered when the relationship between a coach and a player broke down and the goals and communications became unclear. Furthermore, a coach-player relationship to be effective there needs to be a compatible relationship needs to be evident (Olympiou&Duda. 2005).

CHAPTER FIVE

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 SUMMARY

The objective of this thesis was to study the *Examining the Influence of Coach-Player Relationship on Volleyball Player Performance: A Case Study of the Hadiya Zone Volleyball Project*. The specific objectives of this study were to examine the effects of players and player's relationship on volley ball performance in Hadiya Zone Volleyball Project, examine the effects of players and coach's relationship on volley ball performance of the training center in Hadiya Zone Volleyball Project, investigate the impact of players and general management relationship on volley ball performance of management and the coach in Hadiya Zone Volleyball Project.

Finally, the findings are presented as follows:

- ❖ Majority of the participant players were encouraged by the coach to improve confidence, close and informal relationships;
- ❖ From the findings obtained through the questionnaire, players in the study seem to have positive relationship with players and the coach. Whereas they were not

satisfied in relationship with the management of the training center;

- ❖ It was also found that, out of 22 players, 15 (68.18%) of the participant players believe that the coach treats to all players equally and fairly. 3 (13.64%) participant players also said occasionally with the coach treats equally and fairly to all players. 2 (9.09%) participant players said seldom but the remaining 2 (9.09%) players said never on this statement. Therefore, most players believe that the coach treats them equally and fairly;
- ❖ Out of 22 players 11 (50%) rated their level of interpersonal relationships with the management of the training center were not satisfied. The other 8 (36.36%) respondents stated that they have not decided on the item. Only 3 (13.64%) **5.2**

5.2 CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions have been drawn: The training center consisted solely of male participants. All respondents demonstrated the ability to overcome challenges encountered in the training center. The respondents exhibited effective communication skills, likely due to their extensive experience. A majority of the participants emphasized the importance of team unity. Furthermore, most respondents actively worked together to achieve their performance goals. A sense of mutual respect was observed among the players. The majority of players acknowledged that the coach played a crucial role in boosting their confidence. Additionally, nearly all respondent players confirmed that the coach sought their input on strategies, thereby enhancing the players' relationships within the Hadiya Zone Volleyball Project. It is better to enhance the players' relationships by making open communication among each other, establishing good productive relationships requires a considerable amount of effort, and cooperation, provide good facilities and equipment. Majority of the respondents had been visited by management during training session. Most of players were satisfied by the player equipment supplied by the management by the effects of coaches and players relationship on volleyball sport performance in the Hadiya Zone Volleyball Project, Ethiopia. These help the center to build relationship between players and coach.

The present study involved a field observation conducted at the Hadiya Zone Volleyball Project

field area during training sessions. The primary objective of the research was to examine the impact of the relationship between coaches and players on the performance of volleyball sport during practical training. Typically, the practical training sessions were conducted for an hour, twice a week. During this period, the researcher closely observed the players' relationship and interpersonal skills, the coaching ability and communication during practice sessions, and the personal characteristics and coaching style/behavior concerning player relationships and interpersonal skills during practical sessions.

Based on the observations made, the researcher noted the following key points: there was a mutual respect between the players and the coach, and the coach treated all players equally and fairly. These findings suggest that a positive relationship between coaches and players can have a significant impact on the performance of volleyball sport during practical training sessions.

5.3. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the data collected, the following recommendations have been put forward:

- The coaches should ensure that there are sufficient volleyball facilities and equipment available
- . They should also provide motivation through incentives and bonuses, fostering positive relationships and enhancing player performance, with the aim of improving overall success.
- It is recommended that most players demonstrate patriotism towards their educational qualifications. Additionally, stakeholders should allocate adequate budget for rewards and various incentives to show appreciation for the team
- . - Coaches should prioritize open communication and mutual respect among themselves, avoiding criticism and controlling statements. This will help improve the impact of the coaches' relationship with the players on volleyball sport performance.
- The management body of the training center should be able to identify and address the fundamental and critical needs of the players in a timely manner, as well as schedule activities that encourage positive relationships between players and coaches
- . - The team manager should maintain effective communication during meetings with both the

players and their parents, in order to foster a smooth relationship among all parties involved.

- The management of the training center should provide high-quality facilities and equipment to promote success for both the players and the coach, thereby enhancing the overall performance of the players.

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